

HOME-BASED SPORTS TRAINING AND THE PSYCHOPHYSICAL CONDITION OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The descriptive research study sought to determine the respondents' perceptions on Home- Based Sports Training and the Psychophysical Condition of Grade 11-Students. A teacher-made home-based sport training guide and survey questionnaire was used to determine the respondent's perceptions on Home-Based sports training. It was conducted at Callejon National High school, San Antonio, Quezon during the 3rd quarter of the school year 2020-2021. Statistical procedures were used in analyzing and interpreting the data gathered from the student respondents. Frequency and Percentage; this indicates the level of the respondents in performing the home -based sports training; Weighted Mean; shows the typicality of respondents in terms of the respondent's perception/home-based sports training and the psychophysical conditions of grade- 11 students; Pearson-r, used to determine the significant relationship between the respondents' perception of Home-based sports training and the psychophysical condition. After the data gathered, it shows that respondent's perception to home based sports training such as functional training, circuit training, fitness training, workout training and conditioning interpreted as "Fully Effective". As to respondent's perception on the psychophysical condition as to physical fitness in terms of agility, flexibility, endurance, power, and speed interpreted as "Evident". On other hand, in terms of strength, balance and coordination, it is interpreted as "Fully evident". In the perception on psychophysical condition as to psychological in terms of mental, emotional and social interpreted as "Fully Evident". There is a positive significant relationship between the Home- Based sports training to psychophysical condition of the students-respondents. It was confirmed that home-based sports training is important for students' physical fitness and psychological condition. The finding of the study the null hypothesis is not sustained. Study may give insights to parents, teachers and school administrator; they would guide and motivate to perform the home-based sports training for improvement of psychophysical condition of the child.

Keywords: Home-Based Sport Training, Psychophysical Conditions, Physical Fitness and Psychological Condition.